

IRISCC

D9.1

Report defining and describing R1 services

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Abstract

Key words

Virtual Access, Climate Risk Services, Research Infrastructures, Catalogue of Services.

This deliverable defines and describes the first release (R1) of Virtual Access (VA) services made available through the IRISCC project. These services, contributed by participating European Research Infrastructures (RIs), are integrated into the IRISCC Catalogue of Services (CoS) to provide remote access to data, tools, and resources supporting climate change risk assessment and response.

The report outlines the onboarding of eleven R1 services under Task 9.1, detailing their scientific domains, access conditions, technical features, and provider contacts. The services span atmospheric observations, climate modelling, aerosol analysis, and related areas, and offer open-access platforms for both real-time and historical data.

The deliverable also outlines the approach to usage tracking, which will support future reporting in WP9.

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Terminology / Acronyms	
Term/Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface. A set of protocols that allow software applications to communicate and exchange data.
ATMO-ACCESS	An EU-funded project supporting sustainable access to atmospheric research facilities and infrastructures.
CoS	Catalogue of Services. The online platform (https://www.iriscc.eu/catalogue-of-services) listing all services—virtual, remote, and physical—offered through IRISCC.
ECV	Essential Climate Variable. Key atmospheric, oceanic, and terrestrial parameters essential for understanding climate variability and change.
IRISCC	Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change risks. An EU-funded project delivering scientific services and knowledge tools to support research and policy for climate resilience in Europe.
NRT / RRT	Near-Real-Time / Real-Real-Time – Timeliness indicators for data delivery and visualization services.
PID	Persistent Identifier. A stable, long-lasting digital reference (e.g., DOI) to uniquely identify a document, dataset, or service.
RI	Research Infrastructure. Facilities, resources or services of a unique nature that are identified by research communities to conduct top-level research in their respective fields. They may be single-sited, distributed, or virtual and include major scientific equipment, collections, archives, structured information, enabling ICT-based infrastructures, or any other entity essential to research and innovation.
VA	Virtual Access. Access to RIs enabling scientists to use their resources without physical presence at the installations or facilities and without selection procedures for users through web-based platforms, virtualisation technologies, and secure network connections.
WP	Work Package. Defined subtask within a project to achieve a specific goal or result.

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents the first release (R1) of Virtual Access (VA) services made available through the IRISCC project. These services are provided by European Research Infrastructures (RIs) and are integrated into the IRISCC Catalogue of Services (CoS), enabling open and virtual access to data, models, and analytical tools relevant to climate change risks.

The R1 portfolio includes ten services spanning a broad range of scientific domains. Several services offer access to climatologies and anomalies of essential climate variables (ECVs), derived from long-term atmospheric observations or remote sensing. Others provide real-time or near-real-time monitoring tools to support the identification of extreme events or anomalies in atmospheric composition. Climate modelling and impact-related services are also featured, including portals for accessing large-scale climate model outputs and visualisation environments to support decision-making. In addition, some services enable users to relationships between emission sources and observed concentrations or generate footprints for greenhouse gases or aerosols using atmospheric transport models.

All services were described and reviewed using structured metadata templates and questionnaires to ensure harmonised documentation. Each entry includes technical details, availability, access conditions, and contact information.

The deliverable also outlines the framework for future usage tracking to support performance evaluation. This tracking will be implemented via the VA management system developed in WP8 and informed by good practices from previous projects. Overall, the R1 services lay the groundwork for expanding access to integrated, user-oriented climate risk information across Europe.

1. Introduction

Work Package 9 (WP9) of the IRISCC project, titled "VA01 – Virtual Access Provision for Climate Change Risk Services", aims to provide seamless online access to digital services crucial for understanding, mitigating, and adapting to climate change risks. This report defines and describes the initial set of Virtual Access (VA) services, referred to as R1 services, now available through the [IRISCC Catalogue of Services \(CoS\)](#).

The primary objective of WP9 is to coordinate and implement virtual access to services developed and provided by Research Infrastructures (RIs) participating in the IRISCC project. These services are intended to support a broad user community, ranging from researchers and policymakers to practitioners and the public, in accessing high-quality data and analytical tools relevant to climate-related risks.

Task 9.1 has focused on collaborating with RIs to gather the technical and operational information needed to onboard these services into the IRISCC Catalogue of Services (CoS) and the IRISCC VA management system developed in WP8 (Ref 1). These preparatory efforts have laid the groundwork for Task 9.2, which ensures the actual provision of the R1 services to users starting from Month 13 of the project (April 2025). As several services were promised for R1 in the Grant Agreement, these are highlighted in Section 3. However, there are additional VA resources relevant for climate change risk available at the different RIs that have been included to CoS. These are described in Section 4.

The R1 services described in this deliverable represent a diverse range of digital tools and data products, spanning real-time monitoring of atmospheric composition, climate model outputs, historical climatologies, and impact-oriented services. The integration of these services via the IRISCC CoS reflects the project's commitment to enabling cross-RI collaboration and promoting access to virtual services relevant for climate change risks.

This report provides detailed definitions and descriptions of each R1 service. These descriptions form the basis for evaluating usage and user engagement in subsequent WP9 deliverables.

2. Overview of promised R1 services

The IRISCC CoS is designed to provide Virtual Access to a wide range of digital services offered by key RIs. The first release (R1) focuses on integrating and delivering existing services from participating RIs that support the observation, analysis, and understanding of climate change indicators. These services are listed in the CoS and represent the initial delivery of digital services from individual RIs, which will be further expanded with more advanced multi-RI demonstrators (WP4) and co-designed knowledge services (WP2 and 5) in the later stages of the project, which corresponds to the second and third release of services respectively.

Table 1 summarises the R1 services as defined in the IRISCC Grant Agreement, providing an overview of their associated installations, CoS entries, and contact points for further information. Currently, two RIs have yet to add their services to the CoS. The inclusion process is ongoing.

Table 1. Overview of the Virtual Access (VA) services promised for 1st Release (R1).

Overview of VA services promised for 1 st Release				
Installation		Service name	Catalogue of Services (CoS)	Contact(s)
IAGOS-DC_CNRS	<u>Installation 344</u>	Climatologies & anomalies of ECVs	<u>Service 597</u>	<u>damien.boulanger@cnrs.fr</u>
IAGOS-DC_KIT		Anomalies of volatile organic compounds	<u>Service 804</u>	<u>andreas.zahn@kit.edu</u>
IS-ENES at DKRZ and KNMI	<u>Installation 370</u>	Climate4Impact	<u>Service 806</u>	<u>kindermann@dkrz.de, alessandro.spinuso@knmi.nl</u>
		Climate Model Data Access Portal	<u>Service 802</u>	<u>kindermann@dkrz.de, khan@dkrz.de</u>

ECA&D KNMI	<u>Installation</u> <u>377</u>	European Climate Assessment & Dataset	In progress	<u>schrier@knmi.nl</u> , <u>eca@knmi.nl</u>
ACTRIS-DC at NILU	<u>Installation</u> <u>337</u>	RRT/NRT Quick Looks (In-Situ)	<u>Service 596</u>	<u>ror@nilu.no</u> , <u>lemu@nilu.no</u>
ACTRIS-DC at CNR		RRT/NRT Quick Looks (Aerosol remote sensing)	<u>Service 601</u>	<u>lucia.mona@cnr.it</u>
ACTRIS-DC at CNRS		ECV Climatologies	<u>Service 803</u>	<u>lucia.mona@cnr.it</u>
ACTRIS-DC at FMI		Early warning volcanic plume products	<u>Service 862</u>	<u>lucia.mona@cnr.it</u>
ICOS Carbon Portal at ULUND	In progress	ICOS STILT Atmospheric footprint service	In progress	<u>alex.vermeulen@icos-ri.eu</u> , <u>ute.karstens@nateko.lu.se</u>
EIRENE data center at UU (EIRENE- DC_UU)	No service promised in 1 st Release.			

3. Description of promised RI services

This section provides a detailed description of each of the VA services included in the first release, as defined in the IRISCC Grant Agreement and currently available in the CoS. The services have been submitted by the respective RIs through structured entries in the CoS and further elaborated through responses to a dedicated service questionnaire (see Annex).

The information from both sources, the CoS entries and the completed questionnaires, forms the foundation of this report. Together, they ensure a comprehensive and consistent overview of the first-release services, which also supports the ongoing monitoring of service availability and usage in coordination with WP8.

3.1 IAGOS Climatologies and Anomalies of ECVs in the Troposphere

Table 2 presents detailed service information on the IAGOS Climatologies and Anomalies of Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) in the troposphere, as compiled from the CoS entries and responses to the completed questionnaire form.

Table 2. Service information about IAGOS Climatologies and Anomalies of ECVs in the Troposphere.

Service information	
Field	Information
Service Name	IAGOS Climatologies and Anomalies of ECVs in the Troposphere
Research Infrastructure	In-service Aircraft for a Global Observing System (IAGOS)
RI website	https://www.iagos.org

Responsible provider	CNRS
Access Point (URL)	https://services.iagos-data.fr/iriscc/anomalies
Contacts	Damien Boulanger (damien.boulanger@cnrs.fr), Valérie Thouret (valerie.thouret@iagos.org)
Primary Scientific Domain	Atmosphere
Availability	Already available
Authentication Required	No authentication required (open access)
Usage Limitations	None specified
User Activity Tracking	Visits to web interface

Description:

This service provides diagnostics and statistics for a better understanding of the long time series, offering the possibility of the creation of a 'tailored data set for ESM evaluation/improvement', and giving the broader context of dedicated campaigns or experiments.

Extended Description:

This service provides access to a set of diagnostics and statistics, aiming to better understand the long time series, to offer the possibility of the creation of a 'tailored data set for ESM evaluation/improvement', and to give the broader context of dedicated campaigns or experiments. The diagnostics consist of a comparison of each month of the time series with the reference period, based on a (multi-)decadal climatology (IAGOS provides data as soon as 1994 for a subset of variables, namely Ozone and Water Vapor), enabling the computation of anomalies and percentile ranks.

3.2 IAGOS Climatologies and Anomalies of VOCs

Table Table 3 presents detailed service information on the IAGOS Climatologies and Anomalies of VOCs, as compiled from the CoS entries and responses to the completed questionnaire form.

Table 3. Service information about IAGOS Climatologies and Anomalies of VOCs.

Service information	
Field	Information
Service Name	Climatologies and anomalies of selected volatile organic compounds
Research Infrastructure	In-service Aircraft for a Global Observing System (IAGOS)
RI website	https://www.iagos.org
Responsible provider	KIT
Access Point (URL)	http://iagos-caribic.atmohub.kit.edu/iriscc
Contacts	Andreas Zahn (andreas.zahn@kit.edu), Harald Bönisch (harald.boenisch@kit.edu)
Primary Scientific Domain	Atmosphere
Availability	Under development (expected 31/03/2025)
Authentication Required	No authentication required (open access)
Usage Limitations	None specified
User Activity Tracking	Not specified

Description:

Service for visualising IAGOS-CARIBIC flight paths affected by biomass burning, including visualising and providing trace species data (e.g. O₃, CO, CH₄, CO₂, NO, H₂O, aerosol) for studying composition of biomass burning influenced airmasses in the free troposphere.

Extended Description:

This service identifies IAGOS-CARIBIC flight paths that have been affected by biomass burning plumes and displays the corresponding air mass back trajectories to illustrate their geographic origin. It offers visualization of a wide range of trace species, including volatile organic compounds (VOCs), aerosol, ozone, carbon monoxide (CO), and many others.

More specifically, the service enables users to select individual flights and identify the sections of flight paths that intersect biomass burning plumes, with detection based on acetonitrile as a specific tracer for biomass burning. Users can visualize cross-sections of up to two variables simultaneously along the flight path, chosen from a set of more than 30 atmospheric parameters. In addition, the platform displays air mass back trajectories, helping to contextualize and interpret the origin of the measured trace species.

3.3 IS-ENES Climate4Impact

Table 4 presents detailed service information on the IS-ENES Climate4Impact, as compiled from the CoS entries and responses to the completed questionnaire form.

Table 4. Service information about IS-ENES Climate4Impact.

Service information	
Field	Information
Service Name	Climate4Impact
Research Infrastructure	IS-ENES
RI website	https://portal.enes.org/
Responsible provider	KNMI
Access Point (URL)	https://www.climate4impact.eu/
Contacts	Stephan Kindermann (kindermann@dkrz.de), Alessandro Spinuso (alessandro.spinuso@knmi.nl)
Primary Scientific Domain	Climate Impact Modeling Research
Availability	Already available
Authentication Required	Guest (open access), Registration for advanced features
Usage Limitations	Registration is approved based on user affiliation and research interests
User Activity Tracking	Web analytics via Matomo, API access metrics

Description:

The Climate4Impact portal enhances the accessibility and usability of climate research data. It provides tools for data access, subsetting, and climate index calculation through Virtual Research Environments (VREs), supporting reproducibility and traceability with Jupyter Notebooks and workflows.

Extended Description:

Climate4Impact is a portal developed by IS-ENES to support climate change impact modellers, adaptation consultants, and anyone seeking to work with climate change data. Its primary goal is to enhance the accessibility and usability of climate research data for a broad range of users.

The portal is integrated with the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) infrastructure, using ESGF search capabilities and THREDDS catalog access. By leveraging these technologies, Climate4Impact facilitates discovery and access to complex climate datasets, aiming to streamline their application in climate impact assessments and decision-making processes.

3.4 IS-ENES Climate Model Data Access Portal

Table 5 presents detailed service information on the IS-ENES Climate Model Data Access Portal as compiled from the CoS entries and responses to the completed questionnaire form.

Table 5. Service information about IS-ENES Climate Model Data Access Portal.

Service information	
Field	Information
Service Name	Climate Model Data Access Portal
Research Infrastructure	IS-ENES
RI website	https://is.enes.org/services-data-metadata/
Responsible provider	DKRZ
Access Point (URL)	https://esgf-metagrid.cloud.dkrz.de/search
Contacts	Stephan Kindermann (kindermann@dkrz.de), Irfan Khan (khan@dkrz.de)
Primary Scientific Domain	Earth Science, Earth System Science, Climate Science, Climate impacts
Availability	Already available
Authentication Required	No authentication required (open access)
Usage Limitations	None specified
User Activity Tracking	Data access and download statistics

Description:

The portal provides access to climate model data, especially those generated as part of international climate model intercomparison projects like CMIP6. It facilitates the retrieval of a wide range of climate simulations and scenarios for research and analysis.

Extended Description:

The IS-ENES climate data portal, hosted at DKRZ, provides access to an extensive network of data nodes within a global federation. This includes connectivity to European IS-ENES data nodes, offering users streamlined access to over 20 petabytes of climate model data. The available datasets have been produced through internationally coordinated efforts, primarily within the framework of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Projects (CMIPs).

The portal supports data discovery using standardized search facets, enabling users to efficiently locate the climate simulations and variables they require. A range of download options is supported, including HTTP-based data transfer, allowing for flexible and scalable access to large and complex datasets.

3.5 European Climate Assessment & Dataset

Table 6 presents detailed service information on the European Climate Assessment & Dataset as compiled from the CoS entries and responses to the completed questionnaire form.

Table 6. Service information about European Climate Assessment & Dataset.

Service information	
Field	Information
Service Name	European Climate Assessment & Dataset
Research Infrastructure	ECA&D
RI website	https://www.ecad.eu
Responsible provider	KNMI
Access Point (URL)	https://www.ecad.eu
Contacts	Gerard van der Schrier (schrier@knmi.nl) Else van den Besselaar (eca@knmi.nl)
Primary Scientific Domain	Climate Science

Availability	Already available
Authentication Required	No authentication required (open access)
Usage Limitations	Data is for non-commercial research and education only
User Activity Tracking	Not specified

Description:

ECA&D is a data portal and climate monitoring tool for in situ meteorological data at daily resolution, covering atmosphere-surface ECVs provided by European National Meteorological Services.

Note:

The addition of this service to the Catalogue of Services is in progress but has not been completed.

3.6 ACTRIS RRT/NRT Quick Looks (Aerosol In-situ)

Table 7 presents detailed service information on the ACTRIS RRT/NRT Quick Looks (Aerosol In-situ) as compiled from the CoS entries and responses to the completed questionnaire form.

Table 7. Service information about ACTRIS RRT/NRT Quick Looks (Aerosol In-situ).

Service information	
Field	Information
Service Name	RRT & NRT visualization for aerosol in-situ measurements
Research Infrastructure	ACTRIS
RI website	https://www.actris.eu/
Responsible provider	NILU
Access Point (URL)	https://ebas-nrt.nilu.no/
Contacts	Richard Rud (ror@nilu.no), Lise Eder Murberg (lemu@nilu.no)

Primary Scientific Domain	Atmosphere, Aerosols, Trace gases
Availability	Already available
Authentication Required	No authentication required (open access)
Usage Limitations	None specified
User Activity Tracking	Visits to web interface, geographical distribution of users (Matomo Analytics)

Description:

ACTRIS In Situ provides real-time data on atmospheric aerosol particles, VOCs, and NO_x, with a time series plotting service that supports rapid identification of pollution episodes at monitoring stations. This enables timely detection of climate extremes and atmospheric incidents through quick visual analysis. Black Carbon (BC), a key absorbing aerosol and short-lived climate forcer (SLCF), is included among the monitored variables for source differentiation and air quality assessment.

Extended Description:

This service delivers both Real Real-Time (RRT) and Near-Real-Time (NRT) visualizations to facilitate the identification of climate extremes and atmospheric events. It forms part of ACTRIS's broader mission to enable timely interpretation of atmospheric composition data across its European network of stations. ACTRIS In Situ produces and distributes real-time and NRT data on atmospheric aerosol particles—including absorbing particles such as Black Carbon (BC), which is important for source differentiation and climate impact analysis. The scope of observations is expanding to include volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x), with a plotting tool that visualizes time series and supports rapid detection of significant events at individual sites.

3.7 ACTRIS RRT/NRT Quick Looks (Aerosol remote sensing)

Table 8 presents detailed service information on the ACTRIS RRT/NRT Quick Looks (Aerosol remote sensing) as compiled from the CoS entries and responses to the completed questionnaire form.

Table 8. Service information about ACTRIS RRT/NRT Quick Looks (Aerosol remote sensing).

Service information	
Field	Information
Service Name	RRT/NRT Quick Looks for Remote Sensing of Aerosols
Research Infrastructure	ACTRIS
RI website	www.actris.eu
Responsible provider	CNR
Access Point (URL)	https://quicklooks.earlinet.org/index.php
Contact	Lucia Mona (lucia.mona@cnr.it)
Primary Scientific Domain	Atmospheric science, air quality
Availability	Already available
Authentication Required	No authentication required (open access)
Usage Limitations	None specified
User Activity Tracking	Not specified

Description:

Quicklook of aerosol profiling observations provides a snapshot of aerosol presence and variability. Depolarization quicklook provides a direct measure of aspherical particles (dust and volcanic), aiding in the assessment of atmospheric conditions.

3.8 ACTRIS ECV Climatologies

Table 9 presents detailed service information on the ACTRIS ECV Climatologies as compiled from the CoS entries and responses to the completed questionnaire form.

Table 9. Service information about ACTRIS ECV Climatologies.

Service information	
Field	Information
Service Name	Climatologies and anomalies of selected ECVs from ground-based observations
Research Infrastructure	ACTRIS

RI website	www.actris.eu
Responsible provider	CNR
Access Point (URL)	https://earlinet.eu/level-3-data/
Contact	Lucia Mona (lucia.mona@cnr.it)
Primary Scientific Domain	Atmospheric science
Availability	Partially available (climatologies available; anomaly system under development)
Authentication Required	No authentication required (open access)
Usage Limitations	None specified
User Activity Tracking	Tracking not yet implemented, but planned

Description:

ACTRIS provides climatologies of aerosol optical property profiles (e.g., extinction profiles) covering 2000–2019 from over 33 stations. A system for anomaly identification is under development, which will enhance the detection of deviations from typical atmospheric conditions.

Extended Description:

Climatologies of aerosol optical properties profiles, including aerosol extinction profiles, are provided by the ACTRIS data centre for ACTRIS and EARLINET stations that offer a sufficient amount of data. The most recent climatological dataset covers the period from 2000 to 2019 and includes data from 33 stations across Europe and beyond. Based on these climatological averages, a system for anomaly identification will be implemented.

The Level 3 standard products consist of climatological datasets aggregated from fully quality-controlled aerosol optical products (Level 2). To avoid biases introduced by measurements made specifically to capture special events, only a subset of data is used. This subset corresponds to measurements performed according to regular schedules and for satellite validation purposes, such as those categorized under "climatological" and "calipso" in the EARLINET database structure as described by Pappalardo et al. (2014).

The data are structured per station to support future updates at the station level. For each station, three types of data are provided: profile values, integrated quantities, and layer statistics. These are available with four different temporal aggregations: seasonal, annual, normal seasonal, and normal monthly.

3.9 ACTRIS Early warning volcanic plume products

Table 10 presents detailed service information on the ACTRIS Early warning volcanic plume products as compiled from the CoS entries and responses to the completed questionnaire form.

Table 10. Service information about ACTRIS Volcanic Ash Alerts.

Service information	
Field	Information
Service Name	Early warning volcanic plume products
Research Infrastructure	ACTRIS
RI website	www.actris.eu
Responsible provider	
Access Point (URL)	No url yet
Contact	Lucia Mona (lucia.mona@cnr.it)
Primary Scientific Domain	Atmospheric science, aviation, air quality
Availability	Partially available (planned full release by 30/11/2025)
Authentication Required	Initially with credentials; then open access
Usage Limitations	None specified
User Activity Tracking	Not yet active, but planned to include visits, downloads, and geo info

Description:

Early warning product about volcanic (and dust) particles as of impact for aviation has been developed in previous projects starting from aerosol lidar measurements and will be made available as graphical tool. The presence of big spherical particles is highlighted and level of risk for aviation showed.

3.10 ICOS STILT Atmospheric footprint service

Table 11 presents detailed service information on the ICOS STILT Atmospheric footprint service as compiled from the CoS entries and responses to the completed questionnaire form.

Table 11. Service information about ICOS STILT Atmospheric footprint service.

Service information	
Field	Information
Service Name	ICOS STILT Atmospheric footprint service
Research Infrastructure	Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS)
RI website	https://www.icos-ri.eu
Responsible provider	ULUND
Access Point (URL)	https://stilt.icos-cp.eu/worker/
Contact	Alex Vermeulen (alex.vermeulen@icos-ri.eu), Ute Karstens (ute.karstens@nateko.lu.se)
Primary Scientific Domain	Atmospheric sciences
Availability	Already available
Authentication Required	Institutional login required (e.g., EduGAIN)
Usage Limitations	None
User Activity Tracking	Number of footprint requests, number of downloads

Description:

The STILT calculation service is used to calculate footprint maps and simulate CO₂ and CH₄ concentration time series, which can then be viewed using the STILT results viewer. Jobs are created and then submitted to our computation server, and you can monitor the progress of these jobs as they are calculated. You will have to log in through ATMO-ACCESS to use either service through an ORCID, eduGAIN, or ENVRI community log-in.

Note:

The addition of this service to the CoS is in progress but has not been completed.

4. Additional VA services

In addition to the services defined in the IRISCC Grant Agreement, a few more existing RI services relevant to climate change risk have been included in the CoS. Some of these services, while not formally part of the first release, are important as foundational components for the development of scientific demonstrators and the next release of VA services. The list might grow over the course of the project and will be maintained in the VA management system for visibility and coordination.

4.1 ACTRIS FLEXPART Products

Table 12 presents detailed service information on the ACTRIS FLEXPART Products as compiled from the CoS entries and responses to the completed questionnaire form.

Table 12. Service information about ACTRIS FLEXPART Products.

Service information	
Field	Information
Service Name	FLEXPART products for ground-based aerosol and trace gas observations
Research Infrastructure	ACTRIS
RI website	www.actris.eu
Responsible provider	NILU
Access Point (URL)	https://flexpart-request.nilu.no/
Contacts	Sabine Eckhardt (sec@nilu.no), Nikolaos Evangeliou (ne@nilu.no)
Primary Scientific Domain	Earth Science, Climate Science, Trace gases, Black Carbon
Availability	Already available, Service 717 (will be adapted for IRISCC demonstrator #6)
Authentication Required	No authentication required (open access)
Usage Limitations	No limits on existing products;

User Activity Tracking	Visits to web interface, number of requests and products created (Matomo Analytics)
IRISCC contribution	Service related to R2 services – demonstrator #6.

Description:

The ACTRIS Footprint Analysis Service provides modeling tools for interpreting ground-based aerosol and trace gas observations. Users can request model runs to generate data products, such as footprints and source contributions, for specific ground-based stations or access existing datasets. Footprint products offer insights into air mass trajectories. Source contribution products estimate the modelled impact of different sectors on black carbon (BC).

The service included in CoS have been developed under EU-project ATMO-ACCESS (EU grant agreement No 101008004). The computations were performed on resources provided by Sigma2 – the National Infrastructure for High Performance Computing and Data Storage in Norway. The FLEXPART model will be adapted to provide trajectories and forecasts for wildfire emissions in IRISCC demonstrator #6, as described below, but the service above is included in CoS as the created products are of relevance to climate change risks.

Description of use in demonstrator #6:

Atmospheric Near Real Time data compiled and visualised together with atmospheric model (FLEXPART) back trajectories and forecasts, providing a 4-d (time & space) distribution of the wildfire's emissions. The service provides information on the source area, affected regions, plume transport, distribution and characteristics in terms of CO and aerosol amount and composition.

The wildfire demonstrator has set up a system for alerting the RIs about large forest fires, which triggers Near Real Time (NRT) data provision of specific relevant data from the RIs e.g. CO₂, isotopes, and aerosol, on the ground and in the atmospheric column, and from airborne measurements. All data will be compiled and visualised together with atmospheric model (FLEXPART) back trajectories and forecasts, providing a 4-d (time & space) distribution of the wildfire's emissions.

The service is using the resources provided by Sigma2 – the National Infrastructure for High Performance Computing and Data Storage in Norway. Sigma2 AS is responsible for providing the national e-infrastructure for computational science in Norway and offers services in high-performance computing (supercomputing) and large-scale data storage for research and educational purposes.

To learn more about the demonstrator, check out IRISCC Deliverable D4.1 Report on the full Demonstrator design (Ref2).

4.2 SeaDataNet Common Data Index

Table 13 presents detailed service information on the SeaDataNet Common Data Index as compiled from the CoS entries and responses to the completed questionnaire form.

Table 13. Service information about SeaDataNet Common Data Index.

Service information	
Field	Information
Service Name	Common Data Index
Research Infrastructure	SeaDataNet
RI website	https://www.seadatanet.org/
Responsible provider	Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences
Access Point (URL)	https://cdi-open.seadatanet.org/search
Contacts	info@maris.nl
Primary Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences, Marine data
Availability	Already available, Service 789
Authentication Required	No authentication required (open access)
IRISCC contribution	Service related to R2 services.

Description:

The Common Data Index (CDI) service gives users a highly detailed insight in the availability and geographical spreading of marine data sets, that are managed by the SeaDataNet data centres. Moreover, it provides a unique interface for requesting access, and if granted, for downloading data sets from the distributed data centres across Europe.

The CDI service provides powerful search options by combining full free search, facet search and geographic search options, powered by Elastic Search, SQL search, and Geo Server. In addition, users are provided with a simple and effective data shopping, tracking and download service mechanism which gives a unique and harmonised access to the data sets, that are managed and contributed by the connected data centres. Where possible, the data sets are delivered by all data centres in standard SeaDataNet data transport formats.

5. User tracking and statistics

User tracking and statistics is essential for evaluating how the IRISCC VA services are used and by whom, which in turn supports improvements to service provision and informs future planning within the project. Usage statistics will feed into KPIs defined in WP8 and future deliverables in WP9, helping to monitor service performance and guide the long-term development of the IRISCC platform.

The VA management system (Ref1) developed in WP8 will serve as the primary tool for collecting and visualizing usage data. It will provide an API to support automated reporting by service providers. If feasible, it may also incorporate additional metrics from the CoS, such as visits to service pages or clicks on access links. Detailed technical elements, including how service usage can be reported via an API, will be described in Deliverable D8.2.

Since most VA services are open access, the collected data will primarily consist of aggregated quantitative metrics (e.g., number of visits, downloads, or service requests), rather than identifiable user details. In line with recommendations from the ATMO-ACCESS project, all VA services are encouraged to implement lightweight user tracking methods appropriate to their type—such as IP-based visit counts, tracking of data downloads, model job submissions, or API activity. Over the course of the project all services offered through CoS will have basic set of metrics implemented, guided by WP9. These metrics will be harmonized across services to support consistent interpretation, while remaining flexible enough to reflect the nature of each service.

As many RI services are existing services already operated by the RIs, a user might discover them through the IRISCC CoS or the VA management system but then continue accessing them directly via the RI's own data portals. In such cases, usage is not tracked by the VA management system. Conversely, while service providers can report general usage statistics for their services, it remains challenging to estimate how many of these users should be counted specifically as "IRISCC users".

6. References

Reference	
No	Description/Link
Ref1	IRISCC Deliverable D8.2: Optimised IRISCC VA Management System. https://zenodo.org/records/15592865
Ref2	IRISCC Deliverable D4.1: Report on the full Demonstrator Design. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13880714

7. Annex

IRISCC Virtual Access Service Questionnaire

Thank you for taking the time to provide information about your research infrastructure and the Virtual Access (VA) services you offer. Your responses will help us improve the IRISCC Catalogue of Services and ensure efficient access management.

* Required

Research Infrastructure Information

1. Name of Research Infrastructure (RI) *

2. Acronym (if applicable)

3. Website

Please enter a URL

Primary Contact Person for VA services in IRISCC

4. Name *

5. Email *

Please enter an email

Additional Contact Person for VA services in IRISCC

6. Name

7. Email

Please enter an email

Description of Virtual Access Service

8. Name of VA Service *

9. Short description of the service (max 250 words) *

10. Access point/URL *

11. Primary scientific domain(s) covered by the service *

12. Technical requirements for users (if any)

13. Is the service already available, or is it under development? *

- Already available
- Under development
- Other

14. If the service is under development specify the expected launch date

User Access and Authentication

15. Is authentication required for users to access the VA service? *

- No authentication required (open access)
- Registration required
- Institutional login required (e.g., EduGAIN)
- Other

16. Are there any restrictions or limitations on the usage of this service? *

- None
- Limited access based on user affiliation
- Quota limitations (e.g., max number of requests per user)
- Other

User Tracking and Statistics

17. Do you currently track user activity on the VA service? *

- Yes
- No

18. If yes, please specify what kind of user activity you track?

For example: Visits to web interface, API requests for data, data downloading statistics, model runs, product displays, number of service requests, geographical distribution of users.

19. Would you be interested in a standardized method for tracking user activity across IRISCC services? *

- Yes
- No

Additional Comments or Requirements

20. Do you have any specific needs or expectations regarding the integration of your VA service into the IRISCC Catalogue of Services?

21. Any other comments or suggestions?

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